

ABSTRACT

Understanding Neutrality in Biological Systems: Analysis of Gene Regulatory Networks

Piedade, G. P. S.¹; Hashimoto, R. F.¹; Gupta, S.¹; Ostrowski, M.¹

¹Institute of Mathematics and Statistics, Department of Computer Science, University of São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil.

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To comprehend the complex relationship between genotype and phenotype within a cell, one applicable model is the threshold Boolean Network (tBN). In this work, we employ gene activation and inhibition data alongside their interaction networks to predict state transitions. One challenge in this field is inferring gene interaction networks. From known network data, we can construct the neutral graph, which includes connections among all functional networks, i.e., those generating known state transitions for the phenotype. Our work aims to understand the neutral space as a means to aid in the network inference problem. By utilizing the CRACKER algorithm, we can identify connected components within the neutral space, thereby reducing the search space for biological networks. The tBN model operates by utilizing a matrix that represents gene interactions (with 1 for activation, -1 for inhibition, and 0 otherwise) and the states of the process, which are represented by Boolean vectors. In these vectors, an active gene is denoted by 1, and an inactive gene is denoted by 0. Since the vectors have a fixed size (equal to the number of genes being analyzed), and the positions in the vector can only take on values of 0 or 1, we can generate all states combinatorially, thus comprehending all system transitions. In our study, we analyzed two yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Saccharomyces pombe*) networks from which we constructed the neutral space. Starting with a sequence of known states (representing the cell cycle), we inferred the functional networks, thus building the neutral space. By employing the CRACKER algorithm, we were able to identify all connected components of the neutral graphs for both yeast species. For *S. cerevisiae* we found $4,64 \times 10^8$ connected components and for the *S. pombe* only one component was found.

Keywords: Boolean networks; Gene Regulatory Networks; Neutral Space.

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